

Understanding Consumer Resistance Across Disciplines: A Bibliometric Analysis

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Abstract

This study examines how the concept of consumer resistance has evolved and its multifaceted nature. Consumer resistance is not just a rejection of a new product or service. It is also a reaction based on functional, psychological, cultural and ideological reasons. For this reason, the study was carried out in a way to cover different disciplines. Within the scope of the research, 230 articles published in the Web of Science database between 2010 and 2024 were analyzed. These articles were evaluated according to years, countries, authors and the number of citations they received. In addition, conceptual clusters were created according to the keywords. A visual network map of the obtained data was created through the VOSviewer program. The findings show that consumer resistance has many different dimensions. Prominent topics include resistance to digital technologies, anti-consumerism for ethical and environmental reasons, and individual psychological barriers. This study reveals the trends in research on consumer resistance over time. At the same time, it prepares the ground for interdisciplinary studies in this field. It provides important contributions to the development of the concept in future studies on consumer resistance.

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Consumer Resistance, Innovation Resistance Model, Bibliometric Analysis

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Introduction

Consumer resistance is an increasingly complex and dynamic concept in the field of marketing and consumer behavior. Previous studies have mostly focused on how consumers accept innovations. They assumed that consumers were open to change and eager to try new things. However, recent research has shown that consumers can also resist change, either passively or actively.

With the rise in social media usage in recent years, advertising to consumers via social media has also become widespread. Being able to view ads tailored to their desires and needs on their own devices offers consumers many advantages. However, being exposed to too many ads or viewing content they are not interested in can lead to resistance to advertising among consumers. Research generally examines consumer resistance in relation to new technologies. However, this resistance is not limited to new technologies. It can also stem from ethical, cultural, psychological, or social reasons. Ram and Sheth (1989) explained consumer resistance through five main factors: difficulty of use, risk, tradition, image, and value.

Today, consumer resistance has become more complex. Digitalization, sustainability, and artificial intelligence have changed the way people experience products and services. As a result, resistance now encompasses identity, values, social roles, and ethics. With the increase in interest in the concept, the literature remains fragmented and lacks an interdisciplinary synthesis.

This study analyzes academic research on consumer resistance using bibliometric methods. It examines how the topic has evolved over time. Additionally, it identifies common themes, key authors, and highly cited studies. The data is sourced from Web of Science, covering the years 2010 to 2024. The analysis was conducted using VOSviewer software.

The core objective of this study is to comprehensively map the academic literature produced in the field of consumer resistance, thereby revealing the fundamental trends, thematic clusters, and developmental dynamics within this field. Thus, the aim is to eliminate the existing fragmentation in the literature, provide researchers with an interdisciplinary perspective, and establish a solid knowledge base to guide future theoretical and empirical studies.

Previous bibliometric studies related to consumer resistance have been examined. There are fundamental differences between Marco Galvagno's 2011 article "The intellectual structure of the anti-consumption and consumer resistance field: An author co-citation analysis" and our current study, which covers the period 2010-2024, in terms of the development and current needs of the field. Galvagno (2011), using author co-citation analysis methodology, systematically mapped the intellectual structure of the pre-2011 period, the influential authors and the nine different theoretical approaches that were valid for that period. This work provides an important reference point for understanding the roots and early main currents of the field. However, the static nature of Galvagno's analysis does not reflect the technological, social and

cultural changes that have fundamentally transformed consumer behavior since the article was published. As such, Galvagno's work does not fully capture modern forms of resistance to digital technologies, artificial intelligence and ethical consumption and the contemporary dynamics underlying them.

The main rationale of the present study is to fill this methodological and temporal gap by comprehensively analyzing the evolution and current status of the concept of consumer resistance between 2010 and 2024. In contrast to Galvagno's author co-citation analysis, our study focuses on keyword co-occurrence analysis of articles from the Web of Science database, revealing current themes and trends of the field through conceptual clusters and visual network maps. This analysis shows that consumer resistance research is no longer confined to traditional approaches such as postmodernism or social psychology, but has moved towards modern issues such as "privacy concerns," "artificial intelligence," and "ethical consumption." Thus, our study goes beyond the static picture presented by Galvagno's article and addresses the multidisciplinary and ever-evolving nature of consumer resistance from an up-to-date perspective, filling a gap in the literature and providing a solid knowledge base for future research.

Conceptual Framework

Consumer resistance refers to a multidimensional phenomenon that encompasses consumers' active opposition, delay, or rejection of products, services, innovations, or marketing stimuli, as well as the accompanying attitudinal and psychological processes. Consumer resistance is not merely the rejection of a new product or service. It also reflects a conscious hesitation or distanced stance toward certain consumption preferences. In the literature, particularly in the field of innovation, consumer resistance is identified as a significant barrier to the adoption of new products or services. According to research, overcoming this initial resistance is critical to the success of innovations (Laukkanen & Kiviniemi, 2010).

Consumer resistance is not merely an obstacle that slows down innovations or marketing strategies. It also reflects consumers' conscious and multi-layered decision-making processes. Recent studies emphasize that consumer resistance is not solely marketing-based but rather a multi-layered phenomenon that interacts with socio-cultural and technological systems (Esawe, 2025). In this context, interdisciplinary approaches have been found to make significant contributions to understanding the cognitive, emotional, and structural sources of resistance. Resistance is not a passive rejection; it is a conscious and reasoned attitude toward certain consumption options. Research has revealed that perceived risks, habits, value mismatches, and lack of trust are among the factors underlying this resistance. Therefore, overcoming resistance should not be reduced to marketing activities alone; the focus should be on establishing a genuine and value-based connection with the consumer.

Resistance to new products and services is a situation frequently observed in marketing and creates significant challenges for managers. One of the most effective theoretical models developed to explain this situation is the Consumer Resistance Model developed by Ram and

Sheth (1989). This model divides resistance into two main categories: psychological barriers and functional barriers. According to this model, consumers are not merely rational decision-makers; they also act based on emotional and perceptual processes. Before accepting any innovation, they undergo cognitive and sensory evaluations. The barriers that arise during this process can delay or completely prevent adoption.

Among functional barriers, the first is the usage barrier. This barrier arises when a product or service is perceived as incompatible with existing habits, difficult to use, or overly complex (Mani & Chouk, 2018). The value barrier comes into play when consumers perceive innovation as too costly, useless, or of low value (Mani & Chouk, 2018; Sangari & Mashatan, 2023). Another important functional barrier, the risk barrier, reflects situations where consumers cannot anticipate or manage potential risks such as security, privacy, performance, financial costs, or health. Concerns about security and privacy, particularly in areas such as targeted advertising, smart assistants, or AI-based digital tools, are increasing consumer resistance (Mou & Meng, 2024).

From a psychological barrier perspective, the tradition barrier ranks first. This barrier arises when innovation conflicts with values, habits, or offline behavior patterns that consumers have long embraced (Mani & Chouk, 2018). For example, the need for face-to-face interaction in mobile financial services may cause some individuals to resist such innovations (Chemingui & Ben Lallouna, 2013). Similar situations are also observed in areas such as cryptocurrency payments and sustainable fashion. Consumers prefer to stick to traditional methods, which makes the adoption of innovations more difficult and increases the impact of the tradition barrier (Sangari & Mashatan, 2023; Busalim et al., 2025).

Image barriers arise when a product or service does not align with an individual's self-perception, social identity, or lifestyle (Mani & Chouk, 2018; Sangari & Mashatan, 2023). These barriers are particularly important in digital innovations. When an individual cannot identify with the identity represented by technology, they may resist it. Talwar and colleagues (2020) identified image barrier as the strongest psychological reason for resistance to digital technologies.

Just as it is effective in all areas, globalization also has effects on consumer behavior. In a study by Małecka and Pfajfar examining the multidimensional structure of consumer resistance within the context of global consumer culture, the various tendencies underlying resistance were defined as manifesting across a broad spectrum at micro, meso, and macro levels. The intensity of resistance has been conceptualized in two basic dimensions: active and passive. Micro-level resistance targets certain products and brands due to personal differences or negative brand associations. The meso level targets marketing practices by rejecting specific advertising methods. The macro level targets broader systemic structures, such as global consumer culture, in the broadest sense.

Technological developments and innovative products bring many innovations, but it is also known that consumers resist using these products. In this context, the incompatibility of an innovation with previously used products and systems and the learning effort required to use the new product also emerge as barriers to use. In addition, the perceived incompatibility

between the benefits provided by the innovation and the cost of adopting it manifests itself as a value barrier. Uncertainty and potential dangers in the adoption of innovation can also create resistance based on financial and social security concerns among consumers. The conflict consumers may experience with their value systems and past experiences can also create a tradition barrier; the complexity of using a service can also create consumer resistance based on an image barrier (Uddin et al., 2024).

Understanding the factors that influence consumer resistance enables businesses to design more effective product and marketing strategies (Claudy et al., 2014). Therefore, traditional methods that merely encourage adoption are not sufficient to overcome resistance. It is necessary to develop specific strategies that focus on the dynamics of resistance.

Advanced large language models (LLMs) and AI-powered marketing applications use more sophisticated algorithms to predict and guide consumer behavior. However, the recommendations offered by such systems can sometimes be perceived by consumers as overly intrusive or manipulative. Li et al. (2025) define this situation as “perceived cognitive interference” and note that it creates a new dimension of resistance. In particular, the feeling that the consumer's freedom of choice is threatened in interactions with artificial intelligence can increase resistance behaviors.

Although personalized experiences and recommendations may appear user-friendly, they do not always resonate with consumers. Particularly in Web 3.0 environments, some individuals find these forms of personalization incompatible with their values, leading to resistance based on “value misalignment.” This situation becomes even more pronounced when it creates the perception that the personalization process is driven by commercial gain rather than consumer benefit. Therefore, it is crucial for marketers to design their personalization strategies with a value-based approach (Li et al., 2025).

There are several effective ways to reduce consumer resistance. Increasing the perception of security and privacy is one such method. Simplifying product usage is also important. Additionally, offering personalized solutions can reduce resistance levels (Longoni et al., 2019). Resistance factors can have different effects in each market and consumer group. Analyzing these differences enables the development of more effective marketing and communication strategies.

Today, forms of consumer resistance shaped by digital platforms (e.g., resistance to algorithmic bias, data privacy demands) have become a rising area in the literature. However, the lack of theoretical frameworks in these areas is striking (Esawe, 2025). In this context, it is necessary to address new forms of resistance arising from digitalization in a more systematic manner, in addition to traditional barriers.

Method and Findings

In this study, bibliometric analysis was chosen as the primary method because it offers the possibility of systematically and objectively mapping the intellectual structure of a research field. Unlike traditional literature reviews, which involve subjective selection and interpretation, bibliometric methods enable quantitative analysis of large pools of academic publications. This makes it possible to identify the main thematic clusters, influential authors, leading journals, collaboration networks, and emerging trends in the relevant field. In particular, in the context of the concept of “consumer resistance,” which has a multidisciplinary nature and has been interpreted in different ways over time, bibliometric analysis has been evaluated as a powerful method for examining this development from an interdisciplinary perspective.

There are several key reasons for choosing Web of Science (WoS) as a source of data. First, WoS is one of the most reputable and comprehensive citation databases covering high-quality, peer-reviewed journals. WoS's strict indexing criteria ensure that included publications meet academic standards, thereby increasing the reliability of bibliometric outputs. Second, WoS provides rich metadata such as author institutions, keywords, citation counts, and subject categories. These data are critical for creating meaningful and accurate bibliometric maps. WoS's subject categories are specifically selected to reflect the interdisciplinary nature of research. The Business and Management categories focus on marketing and consumer behavior; Psychology addresses individual and emotional dimensions; Sociology examines cultural and social impacts; Ethics addresses value-driven sensitivities such as sustainability and justice; and Communication helps understand how resistance spreads in digital environments like social media.

As a result, the bibliometric analysis method supported by the robust infrastructure provided by WoS was considered the most appropriate approach for systematically discovering research trends in the field of consumer resistance and providing a structured basis for future studies. This study utilized data obtained from the Web of Science (WoS) database. WoS was selected due to its inclusion of reliable, peer-reviewed academic articles and its provision of research search and analysis tools. VOSviewer software was used to create maps and identify trends. The term “consumer resistance” was searched in the “Subject” section of WoS. This search yielded 462 results, 393 of which were original research articles. To focus solely on recent studies, only articles published between 2010 and 2024 were included. After this filtering, 361 articles remained.

To better understand the topic, several subject categories were selected in WoS. These categories helped to illustrate both the personal and social aspects of consumer resistance. Business and Management was selected because it focuses on marketing and consumer behavior. Psychology was added to examine individual and emotional factors. Sociology was included to see how culture and social groups affect resistance. Ethics was added because many consumers place importance on issues such as sustainability and justice. Communication was also included to understand how resistance spreads in online environments such as social media.

These areas have helped to provide a broader perspective on consumer resistance. Rather than focusing on a single area, the study looked at many different aspects of the topic. As a result, 230 articles were selected for detailed analysis. The research aimed to answer the following questions.

- How has the number of academic publications on consumer resistance changed over the years?
- What is the country-wise distribution of publications in this field?
- Who are the most influential authors contributing to the topic of consumer resistance?
- Which publications on consumer resistance have received the highest number of citations?
- What are the most frequently used keywords in the consumer resistance literature?

The table below presents the publication years and their corresponding total numbers.

Table 1: Years of Publication and Number of Publications

Publication Year	Total Number of Publications
2024	26
2023	21
2022	21
2021	21
2020	12
2019	15
2018	9
2017	11
2016	7
2015	17
2014	14
2013	11
2012	8
2011	20
2010	8

Source: Prepared by the authors

According to the table above, the annual distribution of articles published between 2010 and 2024 on consumer resistance shows a steadily growing interest in this topic. Although the number of publications was relatively low between 2010 and 2015, there has been a continuous increase since 2020, reaching its highest point in 2024.

Table 2: Countries of Publication

Country	Number of Publications
1-Usa	44
2-France	36
3-England	23
4-Germany	21
5-Peoples R China	20
6-India	19
7-Australia	14
8-Finland	14
9-Brazil	13
10-Italy – New Zealand	10

Source: Prepared by the authors

When examining the country-wise distribution of publications on the topic of consumer resistance, it is observed that the highest number of publications originates from the United States (44). This is followed by France (36), the United Kingdom (23), Germany (21), the People's Republic of China (20), and India (19). Australia and Finland have each contributed an equal number of publications (14). Brazil (13), along with Italy and New Zealand (10 each), are also represented in the list. These figures indicate that publications on consumer resistance are concentrated in specific countries. The following table presents the authors and their respective number of publications.

Table 3: Authors and Number of Publications

Author	Number of Publications
<i>Heidenreich S</i>	8
<i>Mani Z</i>	6
<i>Chouk I</i>	5
<i>Abbas M</i>	3
<i>De Souza-leao ALM</i>	3
<i>Dhir A</i>	3
<i>Kaur P</i>	3
<i>Mou YP</i>	3
<i>Moura BM</i>	3
<i>Rana NP</i>	3

Source: Prepared by the authors

When looking at the authors who have published the most on consumer resistance, Heidenreich S is the top author with 8 publications. Mani Z follows with 6 publications, and Chouk I has 5. Abbas M, De Souza-Leao ALM, Dhir A, Kaur P, Mou YP, Moura BM, and Rana NP have each written 3 publications. These authors are seen as important in this field. The next table shows the most cited articles on consumer resistance.

Table 4: Publications and Citation Counts

Publication	Citation Count
1- " <i>Resistance to Medical Artificial Intelligence</i> "	833
2- " <i>Consumer adoption versus rejection decisions in seemingly similar service innovations: The case of the Internet and mobile banking</i> "	416
3- " <i>Consumer resistance to innovation-a behavioral reasoning perspective</i> "	394
4- " <i>Alternative marketplaces in the 21st century: Building community through sharing events</i> "	341
5- " <i>Sharing as a form of anti-consumption? An examination of toy library users</i> "	259
6- " <i>Why don't consumers consume ethically?</i> "	232
7- " <i>Consumer Resistance to Innovation in Services: Challenges and Barriers in the Internet of Things Era</i> "	224
8- " <i>Inside the sustainable consumption theoretical toolbox: Critical concepts for sustainability, consumption, and marketing</i> "	213

9- <i>“How to Overcome Pro-Change Bias: Incorporating Passive and Active Innovation Resistance in Innovation Decision Models”</i>	207
10- <i>“Narrative and Persuasion in Fashion Advertising”</i>	201

Source: Prepared by the authors

The most cited article in the literature is titled *“Resistance to Medical Artificial Intelligence”* with 833 citations. This study focuses on why people resist AI-based healthcare services. It uses the idea of “uniqueness neglect” to explain why some reject AI systems. The research includes nine experiments. These show that people prefer healthcare services from humans more than from AI. They see AI services as less valuable and less sensitive to their personal needs. Resistance is stronger among people who see themselves as “unique.” The study also explains how to reduce this resistance. For example, using personalized messages or showing AI as a helper can be effective. In addition, the study offers useful insights into how trust, privacy, and personal identity affect the acceptance of AI in healthcare.

The second most cited article is *“Consumer adoption versus rejection decisions in seemingly similar service innovations: The case of the Internet and mobile banking”* with 416 citations. This study explains that consumer resistance is a normal part of the innovation process. It also says that dealing with this resistance is an important step before people start using a new service. The research looks at five main barriers: risk, usage, tradition, image and value. It also looks at demographic factors such as gender, age, and income. The study examines how these factors and barriers shape people’s choices to accept or avoid Internet and mobile banking.

The third most cited article is *“Consumer resistance to innovation – a behavioral reasoning perspective”*, with 394 citations. The study points out that people consider both acceptance and rejection when facing new innovations. The authors argue that most current theories mainly focus on acceptance and overlook the reasons behind rejection. To solve this problem, the study uses Behavioral Reasoning Theory (BRT). This theory helps explain both why people accept and why they resist innovations in one complete model.

The fourth most cited article, *“Alternative marketplaces in the 21st century,”* has 341 citations. It examines sharing events like *Really Really Free Markets (RRFM)* as a way to resist traditional consumerism. These events started with anarchist movements but later spread to raise awareness on sustainability and overconsumption. People share items without expecting anything in return, which builds a sense of community. The study shows that consumption can be a social and ideological act, not just an economic one. It highlights the collective nature of consumer resistance.

The article *“Sharing as a form of anti-consumption?”* is the fifth most cited, with 259 citations. It explores why people use toy libraries and how sharing helps them avoid regular consumption. The study identifies four user types: Socialites, Market Avoiders, Passive Members and Quiet Anti-Consumers. It shows that sharing can be more than saving money—it can also reflect anti-consumption values and support alternative market systems.

Ranked sixth with 232 citations, the article *"Why don't consumers consume ethically?"* explores why people often don't follow through on their ethical values when shopping. Although many say they care about ethical products, they still buy from unethical sources. Based on interviews in eight countries, the study finds three main reasons: focusing on price, believing the government is responsible for ethics, and thinking unethical practices help economic growth. The study highlights the gap between personal values and real-life choices, showing that consumer resistance is shaped by both personal and structural factors.

Ranked seventh with 224 citations, the article *"Consumer Resistance to Innovation in Services: Challenges and Barriers in the Internet of Things Era"* explains why people resist smart services in the age of the Internet of Things (IoT). The study is based on Ram and Sheth's model and includes functional, psychological, and personal barriers. It shows that fear of technology, personal beliefs, and negative opinions strongly affect resistance. One important result is that people's doubts about IoT devices help explain why they resist. The study highlights that resistance is shaped not just by how a service works, but also by personal attitudes and beliefs.

The article *"Inside the Sustainable Consumption Theoretical Toolbox: Critical Concepts for Sustainability, Consumption, and Marketing"* ranks 8th with 213 citations. It offers a theoretical base for studying sustainable consumption in marketing. The paper looks at three key ideas: anti-consumption, responsible consumption, and mindful consumption. It explains how each helps us understand how people take part in sustainable behavior. The study also shows that consumer resistance can target not only new products but also old habits of consumption. This offers a fresh way to think about how sustainability, marketing, and consumption are connected.

Ranked ninth with 207 citations, the article *"How to Overcome Pro-Change Bias"* questions the belief that consumers always support innovation. The study shows that many people reject new products without even trying them. It explains two types of resistance. Passive resistance happens before evaluating the product and is based on a general reluctance. Active resistance comes after the product is reviewed and rejected. The article argues that resistance is not just a barrier. It is a natural part of the decision-making process. This view helps marketers focus on resistance from the early stages of innovation planning.

Ranked 10th with 201 citations, the article *"Narrative and Persuasion in Fashion Advertising"* explores how storytelling in ads can reduce consumer resistance. The study focuses on fashion ads and shows that even though ads are usually seen as too persuasive, they can still create narrative engagement. This is done through strong visual elements, especially grotesque imagery. The research identifies five ways consumers respond to ads: acting, identifying, emotional reaction, narrative transportation, and deep immersion. Instead of increasing brand evaluation directly, these responses strengthen the brand experience. The study highlights how aesthetic features can change resistance and offers a new view on the link between advertising and consumer psychology.

An analysis of the ten most cited studies on consumer resistance from 2010 to 2024 shows that resistance is not only about rejecting products or technologies. It is a complex issue linked to

ethics, society, ideology, and aesthetics. In particular, resistance to new technologies like AI-based healthcare and the Internet of Things shows that consumers consider factors such as personalization, trust, and control. In the financial sector, innovations like internet and mobile banking also face resistance. However, the reasons differ. Consumers are influenced by concerns about value, tradition, and brand image.

Some studies criticize traditional adoption models. They point out that negative attitudes toward innovation can form before using a product (passive resistance), not just after (active resistance). These studies use different theories, such as Behavioral Reasoning Theory, to better explain consumer behavior. Also, anti-consumption movements and sharing-based markets are seen as more than economic actions. They reflect community values, social unity, and anti-market ideas. Resistance to ethical consumption often comes from a conflict between personal values and larger system limits.

In fashion ads, the use of narrative and aesthetics shows that resistance can be reduced through emotional and visual appeal, not just logic. Studies on sustainable consumption also offer new ideas. They separate responsible, mindful, and anti-consumption behaviors to build a more complete understanding. Overall, recent research shows that consumer resistance is no longer seen as only a logical reaction. Instead, it includes emotional, cultural, and situational factors.

To find the most common keywords in the consumer resistance literature, data from the Web of Science (WoS) database were analyzed using VOSviewer software. A co-occurrence network was created in VOSviewer to show how often keywords appeared together. This helped to highlight the key concepts in the field. A threshold was set so that only keywords that appeared at least twice were included. Based on this rule, 16 out of 196 total keywords were selected for analysis.

The main reason for choosing this threshold was to focus on keywords that appear more than once in the literature. These repeated terms help form meaningful concept groups. This also makes the visual map clearer and easier to understand. In bibliometric studies, using keywords that appear only once can spread the data too widely. This may make it harder to find clear patterns. So, using only keywords that appeared at least twice was a good way to keep the data reliable and the analysis clear.

The keyword co-occurrence network shown in Figure 1 is based on this analysis.

Figure 1: Consumer Resistance Network Map

Source: prepared by the authors using VOSviewer

This keyword co-occurrence network shows the most common terms related to “consumer resistance” from 2010 to 2024. It was created with VOSviewer software and is based on how often the keywords appeared together and when they were used.

The term *consumer resistance* is at the center of the network. It has strong links with all other keywords and shows the main focus of the literature. On the left side of the map, keywords like *anti-consumption*, *consumer culture*, *consumer power*, and *political consumption* appear. These reflect social and ideological themes. On the right side, topics related to technology and digital change are seen, such as *innovation*, *smart service*, *privacy concerns*, *artificial intelligence*, and *internet of things*.

When looking at the time-based color scale, it is clear that concepts like *anti-consumption* and *consumer power* were more common between 2010 and 2015. However, after 2018, terms such as *privacy concerns*, *artificial intelligence*, *smart service*, and *psychological barriers* started to appear more often. This change means that new studies mostly look at things like digital technology, privacy, and how people feel or think.

In conclusion, the network map shows that research on consumer resistance is growing in two main areas: social and cultural issues and technology and personal psychology. In recent years, digital tools, artificial intelligence and privacy have become key issues in this area.

The keyword analysis shows that “consumer resistance” has been investigated in different ways. Sixteen keywords have been grouped into four clusters based on meaning and similarity. When the network map is analyzed, each cluster reflects a different perspective on consumer resistance.

The first cluster shows consumer resistance to digital technologies. Issues such as artificial intelligence, the internet of things, smart services and privacy concerns are included in this cluster. This area reflects issues of trust in technology and personal data concerns. It is located on the right-hand side of the map and refers to current research.

The second cluster is about cultural and political consumer resistance. The consumer's values, identity and social standing shape this cluster. People not only shop, but also make consumption decisions based on their beliefs. This cluster is located in the center of the map and connects to other topics.

The third cluster includes anti-consumerism and alternative consumption habits. Topics such as minimalism, sharing economy and simple living fall into this cluster. It is located at the bottom left of the map. It shows lifestyles developed against the consumption system.

The fourth cluster is about individual and psychological resistance. It covers internal reactions and mental barriers to innovation. It contains fewer keywords but reflects current studies. It is located at the top of the map.

Overall, these four clusters address consumer resistance from different angles. They are all linked to the concept of ‘consumer resistance’. The map clearly shows how this concept has diversified over the years.

Conclusion

This study examines consumer resistance conceptually and bibliometrically. Resistance is not only the rejection of new products. It is also a complex situation with functional, psychological, cultural and ideological aspects. The study is based on Ram and Sheth's model. According to this model, barriers such as use, risk, value, tradition and image affect consumer behavior. The research extends this framework and addresses current issues such as digital technologies, artificial intelligence and ethical consumption.

Analysis of the Web of Science (WoS) database from 2010 to 2024 shows that interest in consumer resistance has grown, especially in the last five years. Most studies come from the U.S., France, the U.K., and Germany. Researchers like Heidenreich, Mani, and Chouk have made important contributions. The most cited works show that consumer resistance is not only about new technology but also about ethics, anti-consumption, and marketing styles.

Keyword analysis shows that consumer resistance includes four main themes: resistance to digital technologies, cultural and political resistance, anti-consumption habits, and personal psychological resistance. This means the topic is not just about marketing or innovation. It is also studied in areas like psychology, sociology, ethics, and communication.

The study shows that consumer resistance is an interdisciplinary and evolving concept. However, it has some limitations. The analysis only included studies from the Web of Science, excluding other databases. Only keywords appearing at least twice were analyzed, possibly leaving out original but less-cited works. Most publications were in English, limiting language diversity. Lastly, co-occurrence analysis shows connections between terms but not their deeper meanings.

In future research, consumer resistance can be re-examined using wider databases and studies in different languages and fields. Alongside quantitative bibliometric methods, applying qualitative approaches like content, discourse, or thematic analysis may provide deeper conceptual insights.

Additionally, longitudinal comparative studies can help observe how key concepts evolve over time. Cross-cultural research may offer valuable insights into how consumer resistance differs across local contexts.

Finally, the effects of new technologies—like artificial intelligence, biometric marketing, and the metaverse—on consumer perception and resistance can be examined through experimental studies. These studies would help reshape marketing strategies by addressing changing consumer behaviors.

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